

PRODUCT USER MANUAL

For Baltic Sea Physical Reanalysis Product BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011

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CHANGE RECORD

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
1.0	2018-02-05	All	Creation of the document	L. Axell	
2.0	2019-04-12	All	Updated for the EISv201907 product upgrade	V. Huess	C. Derval
2.1	2021-09-15		Static files included	V. Huess	C. Derval

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GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS

MFC	Monitoring and Forecasting Centre
BAL	Baltic
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
ftp	Protocol to download files
Subsetter	CMEMS service tool to download a NetCDF file of a selected geographical box using values of longitude, latitude, and time range

I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Summary

This document is the user manual for the Baltic Sea physical reanalysis product BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 produced by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service's (CMEMS) Baltic Monitoring and Forecasting Centre (BAL MFC), the data services that are available to access them and how to use the files and services.

BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 is the physical reanalysis for the Baltic Sea using the ice-ocean model NEMO-Nordic (based on NEMO-3.6, Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) together with LSEIK data assimilation. The surface variables are available every hour and include sea surface height, ice concentration and total ice thickness. The other variables, available as daily and monthly means, are salinity, temperature, horizontal current components, mixed layer depth, bottom salinity and bottom temperature.

The observation types used in the data assimilation are sea surface temperature and profiles of salinity and temperature. The reanalysis has been produced using 72-hour cycling, which implies that every 72 hours, all available observations are assimilated into the model before a 72-hour forecast is made.

Information on operational issues on products and services can be found on our [User Notification Service](#). If you have any questions, please [contact us](#).

I.2 History of changes

Date	Description of changes and impacted product
<u>APRIL 2018</u>	Release of product
<u>JULY 2019</u>	Extension of the product to include year 2017 Product files for period 2012-2016 are re-run due to a discovered bug in the river input data. A discovered longitude displacement has been corrected in all the product files for the full product period.
<u>DECEMBER 2021</u>	Addition of static files

II PRODUCT DESCRIPTION:

II.1 General Information about products

Product Specification	BALTIC_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011
Geographical coverage	Baltic Sea: 9°E → 31°E ; 53°N → 66°N
Variables	Sea surface height variations Ice concentration and thickness Temperature Salinity Horizontal velocities (eastward and northward) Bottom temperature Bottom salinity Mixed layer depth
Analysis	Yes
Forecast	No
Available time series	From January 1993 to December 2017.
Temporal resolution	Hourly instantaneous values for surface variables, daily and monthly means of deep variables.
Target delivery time	n.a.
Delivery mechanism	CMEMS Information System (Subsetter and FTP)
Horizontal resolution	App. 2 nautical miles: Delta Longitude: 3' 20" or 0.05556 degrees Delta Latitude: 2' or 0.03333 degrees
Number of vertical levels	Surface layer plus up to 56 vertical levels.
Format	Netcdf CF1.0

Table 1: BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 Product Specification

II.2 Details of the datasets

BALTIC_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011		
4 DATASETS are available:	VARIABLES AND UNIT	NAME OF VARIABLES IN THE NETCDF FILE
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-surface (every hour, only surface data)	Sea surface variations [m] Ice coverage [0-1] Ice thickness [m]	sla siconc sithick
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-dailymeans (daily means, all depths)	Temperature [degC] Salinity [1e-3] Eastward velocity [m/s] Northward velocity [m/s] Bottom Temperature [degC] Bottom Salinity [1e-3] Mixed layer depth [m]	thetao so uo vo bottomT sob mlotst
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-monthlymeans (monthly means, all depths)	Temperature [degC] Salinity [1e-3] Eastward velocity [m/s] Northward velocity [m/s] Bottom Temperature [degC] Bottom Salinity [1e-3] Mixed layer depth [m]	thetao so uo vo bottomT sob mlotst
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-static: contains these 3 static files		
File: BAL-MFC_003_011_coordinate.nc	Cell dimension along X axis Cell dimension along Y axis Cell dimension along Z axis/ cell_thickness	e1t [m] e2t[m] e3t [m]
File: BAL-MFC_003_011_mask_bathy.nc	Land-sea mask: 1 = sea ; 0 = land /sea_binary_mask Bathymetry sea_floor_depth_below_geoid	mask [1] deptho [m]
File: BAL-MFC_003_011_mdt.nc	Mean dynamic topography / sea_surface_height_above_geoid	mdt [m]

Table 2: List of the datasets (column 1), of the variable for each dataset (column 2) and their names in the NetCDF files (column 3) for the BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011

II.3 Product System Description

The circulation model used is NEMO-Nordic, based on NEMO-3.6. It has been the operational ocean and sea ice forecasting model used at SMHI (the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute) since 2016 (Hordoir et al., 2015; Pemberton et al., 2017). In the operational setup (as well as in the present work), the domain covers the North Sea as well as the Baltic Sea; see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map of the North-Sea Baltic Sea area showing the model domain.

At the lateral boundaries in the western English Channel and along the Scotland-Norway boundary, the sea levels are prescribed using a coarse (24 nautical miles resolution) storm-surge model called NOAMOD (North Atlantic Model). Climatological monthly mean values of salinity and temperature are used at the boundary, and it is assumed there is no sea ice.

The turbulence model is a state-of-the-art buoyancy-extended k-epsilon model. The ice model LIM-3.6 is two-way coupled with NEMO-3.6. A biogeochemical model called SCOB1 (Swedish Coastal and Ocean Biogeochemical model) is currently only one-way coupled to NEMO-Nordic. Thus, it does not affect the physical component in the current setup.

The river runoff is specified as daily means from the output of the hydrological model E-HYPE, running operationally at SMHI. The number of rivers is of the order of a few hundred along the coastline.

The meteorological forcing is from HIRLAM (High-Resolution Limited Area Model) with 22 km resolution, from project Euro4M (Dahlgren et al., 2014) and covers the most of the reanalysis period, 1993-2011. From 2012 onwards, the meteorological forcing is from the UERRA reanalysis product (European Regional analysis) with 11km resolution.

The data assimilation method chosen for this reanalysis is Localized Singular Evolutive Interpolated Kalman (LSEIK) filter, which uses an ensemble of model states; see Nerger et al. (2005). It is a multivariate method, which means many variables are potentially affected by each observation. The model uncertainty is specified using an ensemble of model states, which implies that the Background Error Covariances are inhomogeneous and non-isotropic.

The variables assimilated are SST charts from the Swedish Ice Service at SMHI as well as in-situ measurements of T/S (Temperature and Salinity) profiles from the ICES data base (<http://www.ices.dk>).

The forecasting system is run with 72-hour cycling, which implies a new forecast of 72 hours is made every 72 hours, using the best weather forcing.

Figure 2. Schematic showing the forecasting cycle.

II.4 Grid

The horizontal grid step is regular in latitude and longitude and the resolution is approximately 2 nautical miles (lat: 0.03333 degrees; lon: 0.05556 degrees). The grid is a staggered Arakawa C-grid (see figure 3). The dataset of the scalar variables (all biogeochemical variables) are centred in the T point of the grid; at the grid cell node. The velocity components in the corresponding physical reanalysis are located half-way between adjacent grid cell nodes on the face of the grid cell in the respective direction. That is, the components of the velocity vector (u, v) have spatially staggered locations.

Figure 3: The staggered Arakawa C-grid used by BAL-MFC numerical models.

BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011							
VARIABLE	GRID	LON MIN	LON MAX	LAT MIN	LAT MAX	XPOINT	YPOINT
All scalar variables (see text)	T	9.0°E	29.9°E	53.9°N	65.8°N	381	523
Eastward velocity	U	As above					
Northward velocity	V	As above					

Table 3: Description of the staggered grid and spatial coverage for each variable

II.5 Domain coverage

The blue area in figure 4 represents the spatial coverage of the BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 product.

Figure 4: Spatial coverage of the BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 product (blue zone).

The grid type is on a regular projection. The native grid has larger domain, covering the whole North Sea and the English Channel; see Figure 1.

II.6 Vertical Levels

BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 product is delivered on the surface layer plus the 56 native vertical levels [m]:

1.5, 4.5, 7.5, 10.6, 13.7, 16.7, 19.9, 23.1, 26.3, 29.6, 33.0, 36.5, 40.1, 43.8, 47.8, 52.0, 56.5, 61.3, 66.6, 72.3, 78.6, 85.6, 93.3, 101.8, 111.3, 121.8, 133.3, 145.8, 159.4, 174.1, 189.7, 206.3, 223.7, 241.8, 260.6, 280.0, 299.8, 320.1, 340.7, 361.6, 382.8, 404.1, 425.6, 447.2, 469.0, 490.8, 512.6, 534.6, 556.5, 578.6, 600.6, 622.7, 644.7, 666.8, 688.9, 711.1.

III DOWNLOAD A PRODUCT

After registration, you will be able to download our data. To assist you, our [HelpCenter](#) is available, and more specifically its [section about download](#).

Information on operational issues on products and services can be found on our [User Notification Service](#). If you have any questions, please [contact us](#).

IV NOMENCLATURE OF FILES

IV.1 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the Subsetter Service

BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 file nomenclature when downloaded through the CMEMS Web Portal Subsetter is based on product dataset name and a numerical reference related to the request date on the MIS.

The scheme is: **datasetname_nnnnnnnnnnnnn.nc**

where :

datasetname is the character string :

“dataset-reanalysis-nemo-surface” for surface variables (every hour)

“dataset-reanalysis-nemo-dailymeans” (for daily means)

“dataset-reanalysis-nemo-monthlymeans” (for monthly means)

nnnnnnnnnnnn: 13 digit integer corresponding to the current time (download time) in milliseconds since January 1, 1970 midnight UTC.

.nc: standard NetCDF filename extension.

IV.2 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the FTP Service

BALTICSEA_REANALYSIS_PHY_003_011 file nomenclature when downloaded through the CMEMS Web Portal FTP service is based on the original file names behind the products. The files are in NetCDF and are named:

CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_surface_“analysistime”.nc for surface variables (every hour, 24 time steps)

CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_dailymeans_“analysistime”.nc for daily means (every 24 hours, 1 time step)

CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_monthlymeans_“analysistime”.nc for monthly means (every month, 1 time step)

“analysistime” indicates the first timestamp in the file.

IV.3 File Format: format name

The products are stored using the NetCDF format.

NetCDF (network Common Data Form) is an interface for array-oriented data access and a library that provides an implementation of the interface. The netCDF library also defines a machine-independent format for representing scientific data. Together, the interface, library, and format support the creation, access, and sharing of scientific data. The netCDF software was developed at the Unidata Program Center in Boulder, Colorado. The netCDF libraries define a machine-independent format for representing scientific data.

Please see Unidata netCDF pages for more information, and to retrieve netCDF software package.

NetCDF data is:

- * Self-Describing. A netCDF file includes information about the data it contains.
- * Architecture-independent. A netCDF file is represented in a form that can be accessed by computers with different ways of storing integers, characters, and floating-point numbers.
- * Direct-access. A small subset of a large dataset may be accessed efficiently, without first reading through all the preceding data.
- * Appendable. Data can be appended to a netCDF dataset along one dimension without copying the dataset or redefining its structure. The structure of a netCDF dataset can be changed, though this sometimes causes the dataset to be copied.
- * Sharable. One writer and multiple readers may simultaneously access the same netCDF file.

IV.4 File size

DATASET NAME	FILE NAME	DIMENSION [MB]
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-surface	CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_surface_“analysistime”.nc	8 MB
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-dailymeans	CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_dailymeans_“analysistime”.nc	11 MB
dataset-reanalysis-nemo-monthlymeans	CMEMS_BAL_PHY_reanalysis_monthlymeans_“analysistime”.nc	12 MB

IV.5 Reading software

NetCDF data can be browsed and used through a number of software, like:

- ✓ ncBrowse: <http://www.epic.noaa.gov/java/ncBrowse/>,
- ✓ NetCDF Operator (NCO): <http://nco.sourceforge.net/>
- ✓ IDL, Matlab, GMT...

V REFERENCES

Dahlgren, P., Kållberg, P., Landelius, T. and Undén, P. 2014. EURO4M Project Report, D 2.9 Comparison of the Regional Reanalyses Products with Newly Developed and Existing State-of-the Art Systems. Technical Report. Online at: <http://www.euro4m.eu/Deliverables.html>.

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Nerger, L., Hiller, W. and Schröter, J. (2005): A Comparison of Error Subspace Kalman Filters, *Tellus series a-dynamic meteorology and oceanography* A(5), 57, pp. 715-735. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0870.2005.00141.x

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